

National PID Strategy

Year in Review: 2025 National PID Action Plan

For National PID Strategic Workshop 5 February 2026

Update covers the period from January to December 2025

National PID Strategy vision

Accelerate Australian research quality, efficiency and impact through universal use of connected persistent identifiers.

2025 National PID Action Plan

Year in Review

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Strategic Alignment

Governance

- National PID Strategy Advisory Group monitored progress of the National PID Strategy and accompanying Roadmap and National Action Plan, providing senior stakeholder advice and feedback to ARDC
- National PID Strategy Advisory Group discussed and responded to policy briefs and research sector consultations where the strategy was relevant
- ARDC played a leading role in relevant international bodies, coordinating and aligning the work of the Australian strategy
- National PID Strategy Advisory Group worked closely with the Australian ORCID Steering Committee, developing Terms of Reference for a 2026 merger of the two strategically aligned groups

National Benchmarking

- ARDC contracted Digital Science to undertake a consultative process with stakeholders to develop a national PID benchmarking framework to measure strategy progress
- Digital Science released the [National PID Benchmarking Toolkit](#)

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National Capacity and Capability Uplift

Stakeholder Action Groups

ARDC coordinated 3 Stakeholder Action Groups:

1. Institutions
2. Funders
3. NCRIS facilities

Institutional Stakeholder Action Group

Institutions represented: 28 (*Australian Access Federation, Australian National University, Charles Darwin University, CHORUS, CQ University, CSIRO, Curtin University, Deakin University, Edith Cowan University, Federation University, Griffith University, James Cook University, Macquarie University, Monash University, Queensland University of Technology, RMIT University, South Metropolitan Health Service (WA), Swinburne University of Technology, The University of Adelaide, The University of Notre Dame Australia, The University of Queensland, The University of Sydney, The University of Western Australia, University of Melbourne, University of New South Wales, University of Tasmania, University of the Sunshine Coast, University of Wollongong*)

Key focus: Identifying needed supporting tools, materials and best-practice guides. Co-designing a Capability Maturity Model.

Working Group outputs:

- **PIDs Capability & Maturity Model for Institutions** - a systemic organisational overview,

assessing existing maturity, prioritising good foundations, advising on essential resources and support, and highlighting the benefits that can be realised.

- **PIDs Implementation Guide** - “recipes” for a number of PID-enabled areas, collating more detailed advice on implementing specific activities found within the capability maturity matrix.
- **PID Value Proposition Resource** - outlines a number of value proposition scenarios, which represent various drivers dependent on institutional context. The resource aids PID advocates in communicating with leadership or an executive audience.

Funders Stakeholder Action Group

Funders represented: ARC, NHMRC, GRDC, MRFF

Key focus: Development of funding agency PID Action Plans to reduce duplication of research, improve researcher accountability and research reproducibility, and to increase the quality of data available (such as to the ARC for any future research evaluation exercises).

Funder outputs:

- [ARC PID Action Plan](#)
- [NHMRC PID Action Plan](#)

NCRIS Stakeholder Action Group

NCRIS facilities represented: 12

NCRIS Facilities contributed as part of two focus groups:

- Cross-NCRIS Instrument and Facility PIDs Focus Group
- NCRIS wide PID uplift and implementation guidance

Key focus: Facilitate PID adoption and practice across NCRIS facilities in order to improve tracking of investment particularly in research instruments

Outputs:

- **Draft white paper** outlining recommendations for Australian Facilities regarding PIDs (i4iOz/NCRIS Focus Group co-authors)
- **Education materials** for NCRIS facilities regarding PID use and implementation
- **Collection of relevant use cases** for NCRIS facilities

National Focus Activity Areas

PIDs for Instruments and Facilities

Goals:

- To adopt agreed national guidelines on the adoption of PIDs for instruments as a precursor to greater instrument findability and improved provenance
- To standardise advice on PIDs for Facilities in Australia as a means of improving accuracy of attribution and connection to related identifiers as part of the FAIR Data strategy

Activities:

- Identifiers for Instruments Australasia (i4iOz)
 - Monthly Meetings, Community of Practice standard development
- Research Data Alliance PIDINST Interest Group
 - RDA Plenary presentation and draft white paper on Facility definitions

- NCRIS Stakeholder Action Group
 - See above

Outputs:

- **Revised [Best Practices: PIDs for Instruments Guide](#)** (version 2)
- **Draft white paper** outlining recommendations for Australian Facilities regarding PIDs (i4iOz/NCRIS Focus Group co-authors)
- **Research Data Alliance Plenary Presentation** on Facility Definitions and use cases

PIDs for research grants and agencies

Goal:

- To increase the discoverability, transparency and linking of grants to researchers, and research outputs

Activities:

- Addressed through Funder Stakeholder Action Group

Outputs:

- Funding Agency PID Action Plans

PIDs for researchers and contributors

Goal:

- Increase the adoption of ORCIDs to enable a more complete understanding of the connections between researchers, projects, organisations, research inputs and outputs

Activities:

- Australian ORCID Consortium

Outputs:

- See AAF update in section 3 below

PIDs for research projects

Goal:

- Increase the adoption of RAIDs to enable a more complete understanding of research projects supporting impact tracking and transparency

Activities:

- See RAiD update below

Outputs:

- See RAiD update below

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Underpinning service delivery

ARDC's PID Services and leadership

ARDC's international PID engagements:

- Research Data Alliance National PID Strategies Interest Group, co-chair
- Global RAiD Registration Authority appointed by the ISO
- International DOI Foundation member, Board representative
- DataCite member, Board representative
- Research Data Alliance PIDs for Instruments Interest Group, co-chair
- ROR supporting organisation
- CrossRef member
- IGSN eV member
- PIDfest, co-founders

ARDC PID services:

- DataCite DOI Consortium Lead
 - 89 organisational members using the ARDC service to assign DataCite DOIs to their research data and related materials. Members include universities, government departments, NCRIS/research facilities, and funding agencies.
 - 218,600 DOIs minted through the service in 2025 (notable: this is 20% of total DOIs minted through the service since its inception in 2012; half of this number are IGSNs minted by TERN)
 - 1,073,352 DOIs minted through the service since its inception
 - 110 million+ DataCite DOIs globally
 - 1729 organisational members of DataCite globally from 67 countries
- Handle Service
 - 20 organisations as members
 - 47,962 Handles minted in 2025
 - 701,465 Handles minted through the service since its inception
- RAiD Australasia Service
 - 10 organisations as members, with 5 new organisations joining in 2025 (including federal DCCEEW)
 - 215 new RAiDs minted
 - 487 RAiDs minted through the service since its inception
- RAiD Global Service
 - Partnerships established to set up RAiD Registration Agencies in Europe (SURF, The Netherlands), USA (San Diego Supercomputer Centre and Lydris), Canada (Digital Research Alliance of Canada) with expressions of interest from China.
 - Operational partnerships established with DataCite, ORCID, and international infrastructures (European Open Science Cloud, Africa PID Alliance's DocID).
 - Integrations with ORCID, RedBox, MyLammin

AAF's Australian ORCID Consortium

Statistics for 2025 provided by the Australian Access Federation:

- 44 Members
- 29,345 new users per year
- 38,325 ORCID records updated
- 22,085 unique ORCID records
- 32,503 unique IDs connected per year

AAF as Consortium Lead has completed following engagement:

- 14 conferences and workshops (participated/co-chaired/presented)
- 32 engagement meetings with consortium members
- 92 community of practice events

Events

National PID Strategy presentations

- THETA Perth
- International Data Week Brisbane
- eResearch Australasia Brisbane
- Research Data Alliance Plenaries

ARDC webinar on National PID Benchmarking Toolkit featuring Digital Science
AAF webinar on funder PID action plans

Submissions

The National PID Strategy Advisory Group made a submission to the consultation for the Strategic Examination of Research and Development (SERD)

Members of the 2025 National PID Strategy Advisory Group

Name	Representing
Caroline Finch (Chair)	Universities Australia DVC-R group
Claire Forsyth, Alison Beasley, Lee Harris, and Clare Nulley-Valdez	ARC
Heath Marks, Melroy Almeida	AAF
Joe Shapter	Independent Member, National Digital Research Infrastructure Advisory Group, and Chair, NDRI Working Group
Judi Zielke	Chair, Australian ORCID Steering Committee
Julie Glover, Kate LeMay, Richele Rasmussen	NHMRC
Lachlan Chislett	Department of Education
Linda O'Brien	Independent CEO, Stawell Underground Physics Lab
Lisa Yen	NCRIS Directors Microscopy Australia
Rikke Anderson, Jarrod Ross	Universities Australia
Semira Dautovic	ARMS
Adrian Burton, Natasha Simons, Matthias Liffers, Lyle Winton, Siobhann McCafferty	ARDC

The Advisory Group also met at various times during 2025 with the Australian ORCID Steering Committee. ARDC wishes to thank Prof. Caroline Finch for her role as Chair of the National PID Strategy Advisory Group 2025 and to everyone who contributed to meetings, working groups, Stakeholder Action Groups and other events throughout the year.